
233. Two more exoplanets: Gaia 4b & 5b

TODAY, NASA's Exoplanet Archive lists almost 6000 confirmed exoplanets. Amongst them are more than 600 transiting planets discovered with NASA's space mission TESS, on top of which are another 7000 TESS *candidates* awaiting confirmation.

I described astrometry's checkered historical contribution to exoplanet science in essay 78, with its series of claims and refutes dating back more than a century. Scientifically, astrometry holds the prospects of establishing the planet's orbital inclination to the line-of-sight, and hence its mass. But, because of the tiny angles involved, and numerous technical challenges, the astrometric detection of exoplanets remains very difficult.

Only five *astrometric* discoveries are in NASA's listing as of May 2025. DENIS-P J0823-49, discovered from ground-based measurements (with VLT-FORS2), is a $28M_J$ object orbiting an L dwarf of mass $0.07M_\odot$ at a distance of 20 pc (Sahlmann et al., 2013). GJ 896 is a $2.3M_J$ planet orbiting a binary star system inferred from radio observations with VLBA (Curiel et al., 2022). HIP 66074 b is the first confirmed exoplanet detected by Gaia astrometry (Sozzetti et al., 2023, referred to there as Gaia-3 b). The latest confirmed candidates are Gaia-4 b and Gaia-5 b (Stefánsson et al., 2025), recent additions which I will say more about here.

I described the discovery of the first Gaia-named exoplanets (Gaia-1 b and Gaia-2 b from photometry, and HIP 66074 b from astrometry) in essay 78.¹ But this small number of Gaia discoveries today stands in contrast to the 20–50 000 astrometric detections that have been predicted from Gaia's full mission astrometry (Perryman et al., 2014). Let me recall why.

¹The Exoplanet Archive lists five exoplanetary systems with an assigned 'Gaia' name: Gaia-1 b and Gaia-2 b, transiting systems identified from Gaia photometry (Panahi et al., 2022, essay 78); the microlensing system discovered from the Gaia science alerts pipeline, Gaia 22dkvL (Wu et al., 2024, essay 203); and Gaia-4 b and Gaia-5 b, these most recently confirmed Gaia astrometric candidates (Stefánsson et al., 2025). Although the name Gaia-3 b was assigned in the discovery paper (Sozzetti et al., 2023), the NASA Archive refers to it as HIP 66074 b.

AS PART of the Gaia data processing, DPAC Coordination Unit 4 processes all non-single stars (Arenou et al., 2023). The latest Data Release 3 contains 800 000 solutions with either orbit elements or trend parameters (whether for astrometric, spectroscopic and eclipsing binaries, or some combination). Of these, 130 000 are full orbit solutions, while 300 000 show non-linear astrometric motion, i.e. indicative of partial orbit coverage (Holl et al., 2023). All will be substantially improved in future data releases as more data is included, and as the calibration models improve. Crucially, many of the present non-linear solutions will progress to full orbit solutions as the temporal baseline improves.

Amongst sub-stellar companions, the DR3 processing resulted in 1843 brown dwarf and 72 exoplanet *candidates* (Arenou et al., 2023). Of these, only 10 brown dwarfs and 9 exoplanets were previously known from radial velocity surveys, all with a reasonable agreement between their inferred orbital periods. Arenou et al. (2023) listed just two with *validated* orbits implying the presence of new planetary companions.²

Other candidates include NASA's astrometric listing DENIS-P J0823-49, and previous radial velocity discoveries including GJ 876, HD 114762, HD 162020, and HD 164604. Other candidates add to the rare class of giant planets orbiting white dwarfs, including WD 0141-675 which, at 9.8 pc, is one of the metal-enriched systems suggestive of the capture of planetary debris.

In independent tests, Winn (2022) found consistency between the Gaia orbits and precise Doppler measurements for BD-17 0063, HD 81040, and HD 132406. Of four inconsistencies, HD 111232 was attributed to additional planets not included in the astrometric model.

²HIP 66074 with $P = 297 \pm 2.8$ d, $e = 0.46 \pm 0.17$, $a_0 = 0.21 \pm 0.03$ mas, and $M_p = 7.3 \pm 1.1M_J$ (Sozzetti et al., 2023); and HIP 28193 with $P = 827 \pm 50$ d, $e = 0.07 \pm 0.10$, $a_0 = 0.25 \pm 0.02$ mas, and $M_p = 5.3 \pm 0.6M_J$. Their sub-milli-arcsec semi-major axes are especially noteworthy, with their smallest candidate having $a_1 = 0.14 \pm 0.04$ milli-arcsec. I am not close enough to the work of CU4, nor the NASA Exoplanet Archive, to know why HIP 28193 is not listed in the NASA Archive.

The Gaia astrometric exoplanet discoveries Gaia-4 b (left) and Gaia-5 b (right). The figures show the orbit of the photocentre, after subtraction of the parallax and proper motion. Black circles show the positions at each observation epoch, with their along-scan uncertainties. Blue curves show 1000 random draws of the Gaia orbit. Also shown are the system's barycentre (+), the position of periastron (red square), the line of nodes (dashed red line), and the direction of the motion along the orbit (arrow). From Stefánsson et al. (2025) Figures 9–10.

IN THE EARLY DAYS of exoplanet searches based on photometric transits, it became quickly evident that even a periodic transit-type signature cannot be taken as unambiguous evidence for a transiting planet without excluding many ‘false-positive’ signals that plague both ground and space searches. These include stellar binaries with grazing eclipses, background eclipsing binaries, eclipsing binaries in a hierarchical triple system, and eclipsing binaries with only secondary eclipses.

Similar uncertainties arise from the Gaia astrometric solutions alone. An unresolved source with a small observed photocentre amplitude might also be caused by a nearly equal-mass binary star, or by the blending of light from physically unrelated sources. More than one planetary companion could also bias the estimated parameters. For these reasons, radial velocity follow-up is required to validate each candidate. Early results have shown that a significant fraction of Gaia’s current astrometric candidates may indeed be affected in these ways (Marcussen & Albrecht, 2023).

BUT THERE have also been successes. Radial velocity follow-up of the Gaia DR3 candidates, using the Hobby–Eberly Telescope’s near-infrared Habitable-zone Planet Finder spectrograph (HPF), also found a number of stellar binaries. But it has confirmed two of the candidates as being of sub-stellar mass, designated Gaia-4 b and Gaia-5 b (Stefánsson et al., 2025).

Gaia-4 b is a massive planet ($M_p = 11.8 \pm 0.7 M_J$) in a $P = 571.3 \pm 1.4$ day orbit, with a semi-major axis $a_0 = 0.312 \pm 0.040$ milli-arcsec orbiting a $0.644 \pm 0.02 M_\odot$ star. Gaia-5 b is a brown dwarf ($M_p = 20.9 \pm 0.5 M_J$) in a $P = 358.58 \pm 0.19$ day eccentric orbit ($e = 0.6412 \pm 0.0027$), with angular semi-major axis $a_0 = 0.947 \pm 0.038$ milli-arcsec orbiting a $0.34 \pm 0.03 M_\odot$ star.

It is worth emphasising the tiny size of the angular orbits, of order 1 milli-arcsec or below. And to note how well Gaia’s individual epoch measurements, with along-scan accuracies of a few tens of micro-arcsec, define the orbits (as seen in the figures above).

ALTHOUGH GAIA HAS so far nudged its way into only five of the ‘Gaia named’ exoplanets in the NASA Archive, it is directly enabling the discovery of others. Amongst these are the important class of directly imaged exoplanets. Here, Gaia’s ‘accelerating systems’, mostly exploiting the 30-year time interval between the Hipparcos and Gaia proper motions, can be used as ‘dynamical beacons’ to pinpoint where a new planet must lie, and to determine masses for previous imaging discoveries.

I described this approach in essay 88 (September 2022), and summarised the systems that had been discovered or characterised in this way at that time. This included the imaging discoveries HD 33632 (Currie et al., 2020), π Mens (Damasso et al., 2020), and HIP 21152 in the Hyades cluster (Kuzuhara et al., 2022), and a dynamical mass for the companion to HD 984 (Franson et al., 2022). Other larger surveys are being made (Bonavita et al., 2022; Kervella et al., 2022).

Amongst Gaia-enabled imaging discoveries since then are HIP 99770 imaged by Subaru (Currie et al., 2023), and AF Lep, located within a debris disk, imaged by Keck–NIRC2 (Franson et al., 2023).

I HAVE EMPHASISED the enormous gulf between Gaia’s three confirmed astrometric exoplanet discoveries to date, and the many thousands that are expected to be present in the final mission archive. As more Gaia data, a longer temporal baseline, improved calibrations, improved orbital coverage and improved orbit solutions, become available, Gaia’s Coordination Unit 4 will be in a position to publish more discoveries.

In the absence of detailed insight into their activities, I will hazard a guess that DR4, at the end of 2026, will include of order 1000 astrometric discoveries. The numbers in DR5, around 2030, will depend on the achievable calibrations, and on the multiplicity and architecture of these systems, but upwards of 10 000 might be anticipated. And within the published epoch astrometry, and when combined with radial velocity observations or others, solutions should be enabled for many more.